

GLOBALISATION: A MECHANISM FOR GENERATING DISPARITIES IN THE SOCIETY

Koushik Mondal

Assistant Professor, Gopal Chandra Memorial College of Education, New Barrackpore,
West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Globalisation is a process of interaction and integration among people, companies, and governments worldwide. It is a process that influences every sphere of our life. The ripple effects of globalization affect every nations of world. The nature and magnitude of globalization has been changing time to time. Technological revolution makes the magnitude of globalisation faster and in virtual form. Globalization functionally erases the political boundaries of different regions and creates a global village. The study is qualitative and conceptual in nature. The researcher has used primary and secondary data in the study. Mainly content analysis technique has used. The study reveals that globalization has positive as well as negative impact on different aspects of life. It helps to create a conducive environment for economic development, societal upliftment, political maturation and environmental concern. Economically, politically, and technologically advanced nations are more benefitted due to the globalization. Developing nations or the regions which are not developed economically, politically or technologically gradually become dependent on the develop nations. Globalization creates extreme competitive markets that directly influence the global economy. Individuality of nations gradually extinct. Small business, native culture, regional languages, and customs are gradually abolishing. It creates an inequality within and between societies. It should be remembered, globalization is necessary for the progress of civilization but it is also necessary to re-think about our native culture, customs, languages, and individuality. Therefore, we can nourish the local issues and promote globalisation.

Keywords: Disparities, Developed and Developing nations, Environment, Globalization, Society etc.

INTRODUCTION

Progress is the nature of civilisation. The rate of advancement of civilisation differs from time to time. At the initial stage, the progress of civilisation started with the invention of the wheel. Then, the journey was catalysed with the introduction of agriculture, industry, and technological invention. At the initial stage of civilisation, human beings aimed to collect food for their survival. After meeting the basic needs of human beings, they started to focus on other secondary issues. They created religion, culture, and patterns of settlement. As a result, human beings started to fulfil their needs from adjacent areas. Initially, it was confined to the region, but then due to the invention of the transport system, the areal boundary gradually increased. However, due to the invention of the internet, the revolution occurs in the field of globalization.

To collect or distribute anything to anywhere in the world has become possible without physical movement due to the internet.

In India, the rate of globalisation varies from time to time. The effects of globalisation influence trade, education, culture, medical sciences, technology, and occupation. In India, due to the facilities of surface ways, waterways and airways, it is effortless to connect with the people of the world. In India, real globalisation started its journey in 1991 due to the adoption of the '*new economic policy*'. The new policy abolished the rigidity of licences and permission from the government. A flexible policy was adopted regarding licensing for business or trade. As a result, a revolutionary change occurred in the trade and commerce of India. Therefore, the Indian economy became stronger and more progressive. Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has increased manifold, and different Multi-National Companies (MNCs) have set up their business in India. Therefore, it can be stated that the real impact of globalisation started in India after new economic reform (1991).

Globalisation connects the nations physically and virtually. Globalisation impacts the economic sectors of every nation of the world directly or indirectly. Globalisation helps to create a uniform global economy. It directly influences Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Gross National Product (GNP), and National Income (NI). Economically strong and stable nations are more benefitted by globalisation. The existence of raw materials, skilled labour and advanced technology helps develop nations to become economically dominant. Scarcity of raw materials, availability of unskilled labour and traditional technology make developing nations economically weak and dependent on developed nations. Developed nations hire skilled labour from developing nations at minimal prices. As a result, they can produce goods or things at minimal cost. Therefore, an invisible line is created between two regions. That may generate inequality that creates hindrance mainly for underdeveloped and developing nations.

GLOBALIZATION : AN OVERVIEW

Globalization refers to the increasing interconnectedness and interdependence of countries and their economies. It involves the exchange of goods, services, information, and ideas across borders. The exchange is facilitated by advancements in technology, transportation, and communication. Because of this tendency, economies, cultures, and communities have become more integrated. People from all around the world come together because of it. Opportunities for trade, cooperation, and cross-cultural interaction are brought about by globalisation. It affects how nations engage and collaborate in the modern world, as well as how many facets of our lives are shaped.

Globalization is the word used to characterise the rising interdependence of the world's economies, cultures, and inhabitants, brought about by cross-border trade in goods and services, technology, and flows of investment, people, and information. Countries have developed economic relationships to assist these movements over many generations. However, as these cooperative agreements influenced contemporary daily life, the term is acknowledged in the early 1990s following the end of the Cold War.

It is true that improvements in communication, transportation, and information technology have facilitated greater human interaction and made the world more accessible. Every aspect of modern life is a direct result of globalisation, which has necessitated active cooperation, goodwill, and peaceful coexistence between nations, cultures, and religions. On the other hand, it has also raised the likelihood of ruthless rivalries, mistrust, confrontations, and unease among the people living in different countries. As a result, it is imperative that individuals everywhere rise above sectarian thinking, naive patriotism, and the urge to take advantage of others for personal gain or other nefarious purposes. Stated differently, global citizens need to be schooled to develop a sense of global solidarity and intercultural understanding in addition to receiving an education that prepares them for living in the world as members of a global community.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The researcher has reviewed different literatures regarding globalization. Sitlani & Jain (2013) stated, “Enormous opportunities have emerged during last two decades, resulting from reforms in various sectors of economy supported by increasing use of information and communication technology. After Liberalization, Privatization and Globalization policy adopted by Government of India in early nineties, Indian economy has witnessed tremendous reforms.” Bairagya & Maity (2014) stated, “In the Indian context this implies opening up the economy to foreign direct investment by providing them several facilities, removing constraints and obstacles to the entry of multinational corporations in India, allowing Indian companies to set up joint ventures abroad, carrying out massive import liberalization programmes through the abolition of import restrictions etc. By means of LPG, there is a significant increase in inequality and environmental degradation.” Gaikwad & Dhokare (2020) stated, “Globalization in India is usually taken as integrating the economy of the country with the remainder of the planet. This successively implies that opening up the economy to foreign direct investment by providing facilities to foreign companies to take a position in several fields of economic activities in India.” The studies showed the mixed effects of globalization in different aspects of life.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The researcher has stated the objectives of the study in the following ways :

- O₁: To discuss the role of globalization on the economic growth of a region.
- O₂: To discuss the role of globalization on cultural diversity and the preservation of local tradition.
- O₃: To discuss the role of globalization on educational opportunities and systems.
- O₄: To discuss the impact of globalization on environment and resource management.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The researcher has framed the following research questions to fulfil the research objectives:

- (i) How does globalization affect the economic growth of a region?

- (ii) How does globalization influence cultural diversity and the preservation of local tradition?
- (iii) How does globalization affect the educational opportunities and system?
- (iv) How does globalization impact the environment and resource management?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a qualitative and conceptual approach. Primary and secondary data were used. The study was descriptive. The researcher used qualitative and quantitative data in the study. The researcher gathered data from government reports, journals, periodicals, and electronic content. The researcher used the content analysis technique of qualitative data analysis. The study was conducted in the context of India.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher analysed and discussed the data based on the following points:

Globalization and Economic Growth : The nature of economic growth depends on the stage of the economy of the nation. The rate of economic growth is slow if the country depends on a primary economy, and there is a probability of a high rate of economic development when the economy of the nation depends on a secondary, tertiary, or quaternary economy. Economic development is slow in India due to dependency on the primary economy. Singh (2021) stated “Prior globalisation, there were so many restrictions on inflow of foreign investment in the country. After 1991, the rules regarding foreign direct investment (FDI) have been relaxed. Now many any sectors of the economy are opened for 100 per cent FDI. These measures are attracting various progressive multinational organisations in India. Government has liberalised its norms related to the import of technology in the country.”

Globalization affects the economic growth of the nations globally. It opens the door to connections and collaboration. It works as a catalyst for development. Globalization creates inequalities in economic growth among different nations. Developed nations (US, Canada, Germany, etc.) can optimally use the technological advantages and human resources for development due to globalization. Developing and underdeveloped nations also take advantage of globalization, but due to the weak economy and low human resources, countries are unable to use optimum utilisation of the globalization. Globalization also creates regional imbalances within a region or nation. In India, regional imbalances are also found due to globalization. Urban areas are more benefitted as compared to rural areas. It can be stated that the impact of globalization creates an imbalance in economic growth.

Per capita income is one of the main determinants that reflect the living status of the people. Due to the effects of globalisation, the income of the people has increased manifold. Sources of income also increase. As a result, the disparities increase between nations. A massive difference found in per capita income between developed and developing nations. Income inequalities also found at regional levels. In India, per capita income is high among the people of Goa, Sikkim, and Delhi and low in Bihar and Uttar Pradesh. Therefore, due to the

waves of globalization, income inequality increases at the regional, national, and international levels.

Raw materials, human resources, and advanced technologies are essential for industrial development. Globalization makes it easy to transfer and exchange the mentioned materials. As a result, economically stable and rich nations easily benefit from it. It automatically creates inequality among nations as well as regions. Globalization helps to transfer and exchange ideas and knowledge that are helpful to adopt the latest and updated ideas and knowledge that would promote a sustainable economy. A huge number of ‘*brain drain*’ from developing nations to developed nations creates a knowledge crisis in the developing nations. Figure 1 shows the impact of new economic policy (1991) on the GDP of India. The figure shows how the Indian economy changes with the introduction of new economic policy.

Figure 1 : Impact of New Economic Policy (1991) on GDP of India

Source : https://www.reddit.com/r/IndiaSpeaks/comments/13qj1bw/indias_gdp_and_effect_of_1991_economic_reforms/

Globalization and Cultural Diversity: The existence of different cultures inside a society or group referred to as cultural diversity. It includes acknowledging and appreciating various cultural groups, their customs, values, and behaviours, as well as their contributions to the larger cultural environment. Cultural diversity is the reflection of cultural richness. It indicates the importance of a distinct culture. Cultural diversity shows the status and levels of development of the society. Crozet (2017) stated, “Globalization and culture will keep interacting in nonlinear and unpredictable ways. Interactions between both will keep navigating between universalizing and localizing tendencies.”

Cultural diversity started due to colonization and migration. Due to globalization, the importance and needs of migration increases manifold. The rate of immigration plays a role in the creation of mixed or heterogeneous cultures. Therefore, developed nations face more

problems in preserving or nourishing traditional culture, customs, and rituals. Rural or economically weak regions maintain or nourish their rituals and customs mainly due to homogeneity. Therefore, the waves of globalization changed and improvised the native culture of the region but it also helped to remove stereotypical practices of the culture of the region.

Media plays a major role in the expansion of the rate of globalization. Media shows different cultures of different nations or regions. Mixed culture forms due to the impact of Media. As a result, it is hardly possible to preserve and nourish native culture and customs in the age of globalization.

Globalization and Preservation of Local Tradition: Globalization largely influences the native culture, traditions, and customs. Culture is the symbol and identity of communities or groups. It creates integrity and cohesion among the people. It promotes and establishes unity among the people. Due to urbanization and migration heterogeneity of people increases rapidly. As a result, the practice of cultural beliefs and customs gradually becomes scarce. Globalization adversely affects native culture, rituals, and local traditions. Urban areas are more critical for the preservation of the native culture and rituals. Developed nations and Central Business District (CBD) regions more influenced due to globalization. Mixed and heterogeneous cultures found in these regions. It can be stated that globalization creates a vivid demarcation between urban and rural areas, developed and developing nations towards the preservation of native culture and local tradition.

Impact of Globalization on Educational Opportunities and System: Globalization largely impacts educational opportunities and systems worldwide. The waves of globalization imprint on curriculum, teaching methodologies, and evaluation systems. In India, from ancient times immigration and emigration have continued for quality education. Due to the technological revolution, physical movements of learners are not mandatory. Online platform completely changes the traditional landscape of the education system. Completion of degrees from foreign universities is very easy at present. The present education system is an emphasis on utilitarianism philosophy. The Indian education system also focused on the mentioned issues. National Education Policy 2020 (NEP 2020) stated, “An education system rooted in Indian ethos that contributes directly to transforming India, that is Bharat, sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society, by providing high quality education to all, and thereby making India a global knowledge superpower.” (p. 6)

Globalization and education cooperation are closely intertwined. Globalization has brought education to the forefront, recognizing the value of knowledge in society. It means not that before globalization the quality of education was very poor. Globalization accelerates the rate of quality education and its utility very fast. Globalization makes easy the process and need of emigration. A large number of students and professionals left their native places for better opportunities in the developed nations. It enhances the process of ‘Brain drain’. As a result, developing nations lose the resources, and developed nations gain the resources. Therefore, globalization fosters unequal distribution and utilization of resources. Gradually it would create an inequality of knowledge between two regions. Chaudhary (2016) stated that “In the 21st

century, education systems face the dual challenge of equipping students with the new knowledge, skills and values needed to be competitive in a global market while at the same time producing graduates who are responsible adults, good citizens both of their country and of the world. Thus globalization challenges us to rethink not only how much education is needed but also its ultimate purposes.”

At present time due to the invention of the internet, revolutionary change occurs in the field of education. Developed nations improvised various new courses, methods of teaching, and online materials. Comparatively, developing nations are engaged in developing the quality of education. Methods of teaching and courses are comparatively theory-based. Job-orientated courses are less in developing nations compared to developed nations. MOOCs help to develop education systems all over the world with different platforms. NEP 2020 stated, “Research/teaching collaborations and faculty/student exchanges with high quality foreign institutions will be facilitated, and relevant mutually beneficial MOUs with foreign countries will be signed.” (p. 39)

Impact of Globalization on Environment and Resource Management: Environment means the surroundings that include natural and cultural components. Environment (natural and cultural) evolves from time to time from the origin. The rate of changes in the environment was slower in ancient times, but at the present changes is very fast due to urbanisation and industrial expansion. The waves of globalization create a global awareness of the environment. It helps to develop a positive attitude towards responsibility for the environment. It helps to execute sustainable practices. The National Policy on Education, 1986 emphasised the need to create awareness of environmental concerns by integrating it in the education process at all stages of education and for all sections of society.

Technological advancement and transfer of technology affect the environment and resource management. Due to environmental awareness and international treaties, emphasis has given to the conservation of fund resources, and the focus shifted towards flow resources (non-conventional resources). Technological gradation helps to adopt renewable practices, reduce emissions of greenhouse gases, and improve energy efficiency. Karatas (2016) mentioned, “Globalization contributes to economic growth and thereby affects the environment in many ways. It accelerates structural change, thereby altering the industrial structure of countries and hence resource use and pollution levels.”

Theoretically, developed nations have always been concerned regarding environmental issues, protection and conservation, but practically, developed nations produce maximum amounts of greenhouse gases and consequently have a negative impact on the environment and resources. The capital region or the central business district produces more pollution as compared to rural areas. Therefore, a vivid anomaly has been found between rural and urban regions regarding environmental issues.

FINDINGS

Globalization reduces the barriers between nations. It creates flexibility to import or export any things or goods to any nations. Globalization is the symbol of the advancement of

a nation. It has both types of results, positive and negative (Gaikwad & Dhokare, 2000). It brings revolutionary changes in each and every sphere of life. A mixed culture is formed due to the waves of the globalization. At present time the world has become a '*global village*'.

Globalization has changed the landscape of nations' economy. It has changed the structure of the economy (Sitlani & Jain, 2013). Different international economic forums or institutions (International Monetary Fund, World Bank, World Trade Organization) have been formed for better cooperation and collaboration among the nations. However, due to globalization, small nations are adversely affected. They are struggling to maintain the standards of the internal production. Globalization creates income inequalities between the rich and the poor and between urban and rural areas. It increases dependency on foreign markets and adversely affects occupations or job structures. Different domestic industries, such as the manufacturing and textile industries of India, struggle for their existence due to international competition and standards.

Globalisation has a significant impact on culture and education. It is very difficult to maintain and practise native culture at present. Globalization propagates different cultural exchanges and diffusion. It leads to cultural homogenization that erodes local traditions and languages and creates hybridity and a new cultural forum.

Waves of globalization largely influence education (Chaudhary, 2016). Information is readily available now, and AI technology brings revolutionary changes to the landscape of education. Therefore, accessibility of education becomes easier for everyone. It enhances the global collaboration and exchange of ideas. It also develops a positive attitude towards the responsibilities of a global citizen. India will be promoted as a global study destination providing premium education at affordable costs, thereby helping to restore its role as a Vishwa Guru (NEP 2020, P. 39).

The environment is largely affected by globalization (Karatas, 2016). Due to the development of the economy and trade, the rate of urbanisation, and transportation, there have been immense effects on the environment. The greenhouse effect, the ozone hole, global warming, and pollution are the major concerns of the environment. Different international treaties (United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, Kyoto Protocol, Montreal Protocol, Paris Agreement etc.) take major roles in these issues. It should be remembered that a pro-environmental attitude is of utmost importance to preserve the environment. Therefore, it should be conscious regarding the adoption of any policy regarding environmental issues.

Globalization has many negative sides. It creates a divide between developed and developing nations. Developing nations are getting benefits from globalization, but there is a vivid difference that exists between regions of a nation. One of the important issues of globalization is that it does not nurture regional identity, culture, and values. It is one of the major concerns regarding the effects of globalization. India may be a country that believes in "*vasudhaivaikutumbakam*" and globalisation may be a live example of this (Gaikwad&Dhokare, 2000).

CONCLUSION

As a sovereign and democratic nation, globalization influences different physical and cultural components of the environment. In the present time, India has become one of the most important fast-growing economies in the world. A paradigm shift is taking place in technology, trade, economy, education, and culture. India is also taking different population-friendly policies for the internal development of the nation. Globalization is bringing a drastic change in the internal issues of India. Although it should be remembered, it is important to conserve the native culture, values, and regional practices of the nation. Therefore, at the age of globalization, it is of utmost importance to conserve our local practices, values, and local culture along with the adoption of foreign culture and practices for the holistic development of the nation. There is another concern, to take such internal policies that promote the integrated development of the nations and maintain positive relations with the international organisation and foreign nations. Therefore, with the adoption of such policies, the country would become one of the leading nations of the world.

REFERENCES

- Bairagya, R., & Maity, S. K. (2014). Globalization in India. Its Present Trends and Prospects. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 3 (2), 43-45.
- Britannica. (2025). The Development of Indian Civilization. <https://www.britannica.com/place/India/The-development-of-Indian-civilization-from-c-1500-bce-to-c-1200-ce>
- Chaudhary, B. (2016). Globalization and Education. *Globus Journal of Progressive Education*, 6(1), 1-6.
- Dhokare, S., & Gaikwad, A. (2020). Globalization and its impact on India. *Studies in Indian Place Names*, 40(88), 41-48. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/346520605_Globalization_and_Its_Impact_on_India
- Gamage, H. (2024). Cultural Diversity and Inclusion. *Multicultural Perspectives*, 6 (1), 1-16.
- Government of India (GOI).(1986). *National Education Policy 1986*. Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD). <https://www.ncert.nic.in/nep.php?ln>
- Government of India (GOI).(2020). *National Education Policy 2020*. Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD).<https://www.ncert.nic.in/nep.php?ln>
- Husain, M. (2015). *Geography of India (6thed.)*. McGraw Hill Education (India) Private Limited.
- Hussain, N. & Mehmood, K. (2023). Multiculturalism : A study of India. *Madhya Bharti-Humanities and Social Sciences*, 83 (16), 197-201. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371165548>

-
- Karatas, A. (2016). Environmental Impacts of Globalization and a Solution Proposal. *American International Journal of Contemporary Research*, 6(2), 64-70. https://www.ajcernet.com/journals/Vol_6_No_2_April_2016/8
- Medina-de la Rosa, R. E., & Torralbas-Blazquez, A. L. (2024). Social inclusion and values: a study from culture. *Revista Transdisciplinaria de Estudios Sociales y Tecnológicos*, 4(2), 83-91.
- Singh, N. (2021). Globalisation and economic development. *Journal of Advanced Education and Sciences*, 1(1), 34-36. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/370938915>
- Singh, Y. K. (2021). *Teaching of Social Sciences*. APH Publishing Corporation.
- Sitlani, M., & Jain, K. (2013). Globalization: Current prospects and challenges ahead for policy makers. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 2 (10),181-191.